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Environmental Durability and Damage Tolerance of Glass-Epoxy Composites: Adhesion Mechanisms with Ductile Interlayers

5 AUGUST 2025

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Environmental Durability and Damage Tolerance of Glass-Epoxy Composites: Adhesion Mechanisms with Ductile Interlayers

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OUTLINE

- Program Overview – Environmental durability and new resin development and characterization
- Introduction/background – why interlayers work
- Experimental Setup, Specimen Manufacturing
- Results
 - Baseline and Interlayer Peel Strength
 - Bonding Mechanisms
 - Process Modification
 - Validation using FTIR
- Peel strength at operating temperature extremes, next steps

MOTIVATION & OBJECTIVE

- **Epoxy resins** commonly used in polymer composites due to balance of properties:
 - Mechanical properties, thermal stability
 - Processability → low viscosity, low pressure/temperature cure
- Subjected to wide range of operating temperatures from **-51C to 76C**, high RH
- May affect mechanical properties (structural and energy absorbing)
- Materials used → toughened epoxy resin (SC-15), alternate resin formulations (RDL-RDC from Huntsman) with **higher Tg**

<http://www.marines.mil/unit/hqmc.thedrive.com>

Objective 1: Characterize key properties of SC-15 and RDL-RDC, understand fundamental mechanisms for improvement in performance

INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONING ON YOUNG'S MODULUS OF SC-15 AND RDL-RDC RESINS

RDL-RDC 76C-88% RH, 0.1 s⁻¹

SC-15 76C-88% RH, 0.1 s⁻¹

The hollow markets represent baseline values for dry samples tested at room temperature and E_{50} refers to 50% reduction in properties from baseline values.

ENHANCING DAMAGE TOLERANCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL DURABILITY OF GLASS-EPOXY COMPOSITES

Thermal Analysis

- DSC
- DMA
- TGA
- TMA
- Rheology

QS and SPHB Resin Tests

- Room Temperature
- Extreme Temperatures
- Moisture + Temperature

Interface Testing

- Baseline
- Moisture Saturated
- Extreme Temperature

Peel Tests

- With and w/o interlayer
- Room Temperature
- Adhesion Mechanisms

Impact Tests and Models

- Delamination resistance with and w/o interlayer

Resin Flow Simulations

- Processability and resin flow simulations with interlayer using LIMS

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THERMOPLASTIC INTERLAYERS IMPROVE DAMAGE TOLERANCE

High energy (7.4kJ), low velocity impact on 44 ply (~1.25" thick S2 glass- SC15 composite)

Baseline panel
44% stiffness retention
14" delamination

Interlayer panel
91% stiffness retention
NO delamination

INTERLAYER MECHANISMS

Experiments at CCM, 2012

Boyd, Bogetti et al (2018) ARL

- Reduces transverse shear stresses through decoupling
- Improves fracture toughness

Simulation and modeling tools are critical to design composites with interlayers to answer key questions such as: # of interlayers, placement, effective stiffness, predicting delamination and residual properties

This talk

SPECIMEN SCHEMATIC AND MANUFACTURING

VARTM in at ambient conditions

TESTING SETUP – FLOATING ROLLER PEEL TEST

Stick – slip behavior, peel strength is taken as average of force over 4 inches

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- Program Overview – Improving damage tolerance, predicting performance and design tool development
- Experimental Setup, Specimen Manufacturing
- Results
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 - Validation using FTIR
- Summary

BASELINE – WITHOUT INTERLAYER

(lbf/inch)	Room Temp.
RDL Baseline	12.3 ± 0.6
SC-15 Baseline	13.8 ± 0.7
RDL With Interlayer	
SC-15 With Interlayer	

INTERLAYER 10 MIL UAF 472 TPU

(lbf/inch)	Room Temp.
RDL Baseline	12.3 ± 0.6
SC-15 Baseline	13.8 ± 0.7
RDL With Interlayer	25.1 ± 6.0
SC-15 With Interlayer	74.5 ± 19.5

Key takeaway: Why does SC-15 have 3 times more peel strength than RDL-RDC? How do we improve the peel strength for RDL-RDC? Cohesive failure and yielding of TPU → higher peel strength/toughness

BONDING MECHANISMS

- Typical bonding mechanisms for polymers (theories of adhesion W.C. Wake 1977)
 - Physical Adsorption
 - Mechanical Interlocking
 - Chemical Bonding
 - Electrostatic Attraction
 - **Diffusion**
- Focusing on Resin-TPU interaction,
- Glass-TPU could affect too, but same for both resins

Interphase formation

Diffusion affected by:

- Viscosity & Molecular Weight
- Molecular Size
- Solubility parameter matching
- Temperature dependence
- Time (till the resin gels)

VISCOSITY COMPARISON SC-15 AND RDL

- Parallel plate rheometer
- Continuous flow, 1 mm gap
- Shear rate 10/s

- Same volume of resin dropped on TPU side by side

MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND MOLECULE SIZE

RDC Curing Agent	CAS#	%	Chemical Structure
Diethylmethylbenzenediamine Mol. Wt (178.3)	68479-98-1	50-70	
2,2'-dimethyl-4,4'-methylenebis(cyclohexylamine) Mol. Wt (238.4)	6864-37-5	30-50	
1,2-Diaminocyclohexane Mol. Wt (114.2)	694-83-7	3-5	
SC-15 Part B	CAS#	%	Chemical Structure
1,2-Diaminocyclohexane Mol. Wt (114.2)	694-83-7	65-90	

Key takeaway: Diffusion with epoxy is amine driven. Chemical structure and Mol. Weight shows RDL is going to be slower and lesser with diffusion

POLYMER DISSOLUTION IN SOLVENTS

- Typically involves two transport processes
 - Solvent diffusion
 - Chain Disentanglement
- When polymer (TPU) is in contact with solvent (epoxy + amine), a **swollen layer is formed along the interface**
- For typical organic solvents (or epoxy separate and amine separate), after 'long' times, the polymer dissolves
- For epoxy + amine reaction, cross-links are formed, which stops the dissolving process, creating molecular level mechanical interlocking within the polymer

SC-15 dissolves TPU faster than RDC, results below for 60°C

Time (hrs)	SC-15 PART B			
0	1.01 mm		1.01 mm	
1	0.80		0.92	
4.25	Dissolved		0.6	

SWELLING MEASUREMENT IN TPU

- 4 sheets of TPU fused together
- Immersed in a vial of resin at RT
 - SC-15
 - RDL-RDC
- Swelling measured using micrometer as a function of time
- Swelling in SC-15 > RDL-RDC, indicating more penetration and therefore likely the reason for higher peel strength

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE

- Diffusion typically increases with temperature
 - Higher mobility of solvent molecules, Decrease in viscosity of the solvent (epoxy)
 - The ductile TPU interlayer becomes softer and less stiffer
- For epoxy-amine diffusion in TPU though, a competing mechanism is present
- Increasing temperature, increases rate of reaction and cross-linking; increases viscosity
- Voleppe et al, investigated interdiffusion length with varying gelation times
- The penetration depth of the TS into the TP increases with decreasing gelation time
- Stronger thermal activation of diffusion over reaction at the early stages of curing.

Variation of the penetration depth as a function of the gelation time.

Curing cycle	C ₁₆₀	C ₁₈₀	C _{180,slow}
Gel time t_{gel} [min]	70	140	280
Interdiffusion length l_D [μm]	66	33	3

Key Takeaway: If the processing temperature is increased, it could promote diffusion, therefore increasing peel strength/toughness

PROCESS MODIFICATION: VARTM @ 60°C

60 Infused/ RT Tested	RT Infused/ RT Tested	% difference
63.8 ± 13.4	25.1 ± 6.0	154.1

Key Takeaway: Peel strength increased from 25 to 64 lbs/inch when processed at elevated temperatures, mixed failure with residual TPU on both sides.

The time of diffusion depends on the gel time of the resin. ~6 hours at RT and ~ 1 hour at 60C. Therefore, there are competing mechanisms. At 60C, time decreases, but diffusion likely increases.

HOW DO WE VALIDATE INCREASED DIFFUSION AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE: FTIR CHARACTERIZATION

- 4 sheets of TPU fused together and potted/polished
- Pre cure at RT and 60C
- Perkin Elmer spotlight 200i with Midrange IR using ATR, 100 um spot size

NEAT SC-15 SPECTRA → VALIDATION OF MEASUREMENTS

Peak Number	X (cm-1)	Bond Type
1	3384	(O-H) alcohol & (N-H) primary amine
2	2924	(C-H) Alkane & (O-H) Alcohol
3	2858	(C-H) Alkane
4	1726	(C-H) Aromatic overtone + (C=O)
5	1608	(C=C) stretching & (N-H) bending
6	1583	(C=C) Cycloalkene & (N-H) Amine
7	1509	(C=C) Aromatic ring
8	1453	(C=C) Aromatic ring
9	1362	(O-H) Alcohol
10	1339	(O-H) Alcohol & (C-N) Aromatic amine
11	1296	(C-N) Aromatic amine
12	1243	(C-N) Aromatic amine
13	1181	(C-O-C) Ester & (N-H) Amine
14	1105	(C-N) Amine & (C-O) Ether
15	1036	Saturated Aliphatic Primary Alcohol
16	932	Epoxide bond stretching
17	828	C-O-C stretching
18	752	(C-H)

Neat SC-15 Results vs Literature:

* Hosur et al, Mechanical and viscoelastic properties of epoxy nanocomposites reinforced with carbon nanotubes (2017)
 ** LibreText IR Spectroscopy Absorption Table
 + Jin et. al., Design and Performance of Polyurethane Elastomers Composed with Different Soft Segments (2020)
 % Irusta et. Al., Aromatic poly(ester-urethanes): effect of the polyol molecular weight on the photochemical behaviour (1999)

RDL-RDC VS TPU COMPARISON

PEAK 1726 RT

Name	Cursor	Description
Line Scan_(1)_001	0.24966 A	Sample at -2717.00 μm (X), 441.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(2)_001	0.2505 A	Sample at -2615.00 μm (X), 396.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(3)_001	0.2506 A	Sample at -2513.00 μm (X), 350.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(4)_001	0.24756 A	Sample at -2410.00 μm (X), 305.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(5)_001	0.24565 A	Sample at -2308.00 μm (X), 259.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(6)_001	0.24332 A	Sample at -2206.00 μm (X), 214.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(7)_001	0.24214 A	Sample at -2103.00 μm (X), 169.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(8)_001	0.23994 A	Sample at -2001.00 μm (X), 123.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(9)_001	0.2219 A	Sample at -1898.00 μm (X), 78.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(10)_001	0.02602 A	Sample at -1796.00 μm (X), 33.00 μm (Y), -16...

Name	Description
Line Scan_(1)	Sample at 463.00 μm (X), 602.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(2)	Sample at 560.00 μm (X), 545.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(3)	Sample at 656.00 μm (X), 489.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(4)	Sample at 753.00 μm (X), 432.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(5)	Sample at 849.00 μm (X), 375.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(6)	Sample at 946.00 μm (X), 318.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(7)	Sample at 1042.00 μm (X), 261.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(8)	Sample at 1139.00 μm (X), 204.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(9)	Sample at 1235.00 μm (X), 147.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(10)	Sample at 1332.00 μm (X), 91.00 μm (Y), -16...
Line Scan_(11)	Sample at 1428.00 μm (X), 34.00 μm (Y), -16...

Key Takeaway: Pictures show for RT, curves reach 'equilibrium' in lesser measurements that 60C

PEAK 1726 AREA MEASURED FOR EACH SCAN TO DETERMINE EPOXY PENETRATION

RT reaches 'equilibrium'

- The amount of epoxy into tpu should decrease as we move away from interface
- Outside of epoxy penetration length, tpu peak area should be consistent
- Graph on left shows RT reaches consistent area after ~ 100 um, 60C after ~ 250 um

HEIGHT VS. AREA OF PEAK (1726) → SAME TRENDS

SIMILAR TRENDS FOR DIFFERENT TPU PEAKS

Graphs show the normalized area change for peak 1726 and peak 1170 for RDL-RDC & UAF 472 TPU

RT

60°C

SUMMARY

- Using ductile TPU increases damage tolerance
 - Increases peel strength (fracture toughness)
 - Decouples plies, reducing transverse shear stresses
- RDL-RDC a suitable candidate resin to replace SC-15, additional characterization required
- Key bonding mechanisms between epoxy-resin and TPU interlayer investigated
- Diffusion is the dominant mechanism → temperature, molecular weight/size and viscosity key parameters
- Swelling of TPU used as a parameter to compare interaction between epoxy-tpu
- FTIR ATR on cross-section of TPU-Epoxy sample provides additional insights into the interdiffusion length
- RDL-RDC process modified by VARTM at 60C to improve peel strength/performance

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

- This research was sponsored by the U.S. Army CCDC Army Research Laboratory and was accomplished under Cooperative Agreement Number **W911NF-18-2-0299 & W911NF-24-2-0127**. The views and conclusions contained in this document are those of the authors and should not be interpreted as representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the Army Research Laboratory or the U.S. Government.
- Team effort lead by Prof. Gillespie
- Joe, Taka, Paul, Ankita, Shagata, Art
- Interns – Lucas, Kushal, Andrew, Alex
- CCM staff

